

THE PSYCHOSIS OF SHIPWRECKERS

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13958757

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the topic of 'castaway psychosis'. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it expands the exploration of the psychological mechanisms of mental action analyzed and studied in the light of Psychoanalysis. Its social relevance lies in the fact that it will expand the chain of texts available to the lay public, portraying an analysis based on an epic work. The general objective of this article is to analyze how the psychotic aspect manifested itself in sailors. Psychosis is a psychological disorder that requires specialized medical intervention. The psychotic state that attacked the sailors possibly led them to a state of life in the childhood phase, in which the mother was a central figure, because the representations demonstrate a woman accessible only in the nutritional aspect, to which the child has ample access in her lactating phase, with access to sex being denied by a psychic representation of a biological condition of the desired female. Reality can be such an extreme and distressing condition for some that the alternative they find is the construction of a wonderful world in which there are no rules other than those that they create at will and retreat into, refusing to leave for any banal reasons. With sailors the situation may not have been different; Delivered to a wandering life and devotion of a destiny, all that melody led them to represent what they had created in their daydreams and lodge themselves in this fantasy, refusing to leave it, because in doing so, this would deprive them of a state of pleasure, of ecstasy; In fact, this term is somewhat controversial, because no human being can escape from themselves; with only the possibility of entering so deeply into their own psychological world that they start to ignore everything and everyone outside of it and, in the case of the shipwrecked psychosis, they refuse reality in such a way that they even deny their condition of death, or even not caring about her. This is a very delicate aspect of existence, because each person can subject themselves to a psychotic state, depending on their desire, driven [or not] by traumatic experiences and the ways in which they affect them and their state of psychic economy.

Keywords: Psychosis. Shipwrecked Psychosis. Psychoanalysis. Mermaid Parthenope.

INTRODUCTION

Psychoanalysis, understood and applied to existential phenomena as a technique and an art, depends on assimilating content from other fields in order to achieve its purpose, which is to explain why certain events occur to specific groups and not in a generalized manner. It also

seeks to explain how this mechanism works, working towards a possible cure for the patient, an expression that must be very well clarified, so as to avoid the erroneous understanding that, once cured, the patient is free from the illness that tormented him. However, this is not how things work; the individual's ego becomes strong enough to allow him to live in a balanced way with the conflict situations that cross him. If a certain illness exists and attacks a specific gender, for example, the *homo gender*, there could not be, at least in a *broad sense*, a group more prone to this. This could be seen as discrimination, but this is not how things work in practice. Certain professions, certain lifestyles, certain deprivations end up causing various psychological disorders, leading individuals to states of mental alienation, one of the best known being psychosis.

Within the psychic universe addressed by Freud and his disciples, psychosis was one of the psychic illnesses they ended up coming into contact with, because the line of investigation that led them towards the treatment of neuroses would invariably lead to an encounter with it, despite the fact that some manifestations of behavioral disorder could not be explained by the line used. Unfortunately, the Master from Vienna did not delve into it in depth; however, he left a contribution that undoubtedly helped in the understanding of the mechanisms that lead to such a situation of psychic disorder.

One argument that can be used to explain the difficulty of Psychoanalysis in treating psychosis is that, unlike the neurotic, who expresses himself verbally, that is, transforms his condition of intrinsic conflict into words, gestures and behavioral attitudes, the psychotic patient closes himself in his world, which is created in his image and perfection and concentrates there, finding no reason to try to leave it; not even a desire to escape; since his conflict is with the external world.

Based on Freud's interpretation of psychosis, it would be more likely to occur in groups that suffer from insoluble internal conflicts due to their external conditions, for example, the subject who wants to be king; however, his financial situation and lineage greatly prevent him from doing so. Likewise, there were sailors who lived and many who still live in conditions of true socioeconomic misery, subjugated by forced labor on the high seas, direct sunlight and scorching heat. Only one constituent element is missing to have a state of deep delirium, which would be prolonged hunger; but it is not just a lack of food; the scarcity of proteins, vitamins and minerals added to the whole set mentioned above would eventually lead to madness, with daydreams and alienation from objective reality.

For a sailor, living in miserable conditions and for intense days on the high seas, exposed to all kinds of deprivation and bad weather, any element that could act as a trigger would be

enough to lead the individual to a state of psychic disorder and, as far as the Greeks' knowledge went, music was what they determined for this purpose. The wonderful and melodious sounds, in soprano and mezzo-soprano tones produced by those seductive, half-naked creatures, creating an enchanting music, led those rough men to surrender to the delirium produced by their thoughts dominated by longing for home and the taverns and everything special that these places could offer.

They completely disconnected themselves from objective reality, surrendering themselves to an alienating state in which nothing existed beyond what they created as a comforting place, in which they found a peace of mind never before experienced. Legends tell that, once possessed by the intoxicating song of the sirens, sailors would throw their ships against the rocks where they were. This could well have been a mad attempt at resistance or even an act of suicide. Whatever it was, what is clear is the imperious power that they, through their song, exerted over the sailors, highlighting that nutritional and emotional deficiencies became the preponderant element that led them to the extreme of madness, being captured by psychosis and its effects.

PSYCHOSIS

Psychosis is the clinical name given to a pathological psychological state characterized by the individual's loss of contact with external reality and, as a result, the individual begins to exhibit antisocial behavior, requiring specialized medical intervention in order to restore the patient to a state of psychological balance. There is still no consensus on its causes, which has led to much discussion and controversy within the medical and scientific community. Experts and specialists believe that social factors, such as living in large cities, drug abuse and social isolation, may be directly or indirectly associated with the origin of psychosis and the manifestation of its symptoms.

According to Freud ([1923] 2006), psychosis would be a conflict between the ego and external reality. In it, there is a predominance of the self, where the ego creates a new internal world, almost completely denying the existence and importance of the external world according to the impulses of the *Id*, with a distancing from reality due to some intense frustration of the *Id*. As there are attempts to reestablish a new relationship with reality, they occur without restrictions to the *Id*, through the imaginary, delusions and hallucinations. The delusion comes as an attempt to cure or fulfill this reality that could not be supported. The Ego constructs a new

reality according to the impulses of the *Id*. In an auditory hallucination, for example, the subject hears his own inner self, that is, his own thoughts projected in voices (Lins, 2007).

Delusions, visions and voices can be understood as projections of the internal world towards the external world, characterizing them as an absolute truth that, in a bizarre and still not understood way, would allow the individual psychic economy to be balanced, placing an order in the individual's intrinsic world. By taking this line of understanding, psychosis can provide the individual with a satisfaction that would not be possible anywhere else, other than what exists through fantasy and from it. In a way that is strange to us, it can be said that the psychotic is happy with his illness and, possibly, the cure is so complex and so difficult because the patient himself resists returning to his external reality that is marked by limitations, sanctions and deprivations of all kinds. Possibly, as time goes by, the individual becomes more confident that the alienating reality he created from his psychotic delirium is real, beginning to confuse, in fact, his fantastic existence with real existence, beginning to opt for the first over the second because of the condition of egoic satisfaction provided by it.

This understanding would place psychosis as a repressed form of pleasure that, once encountered by the individual, refuses to abandon; even in spite of everything that may be directed at him to the contrary, leading to an interpretation that the illness actually bothers those who are present in the patient's external reality. As always, there will be someone who wants to speak on behalf of the madman, without asking him what his world represents and how he feels and, to make matters worse, when the answer does not satisfy the interlocutor, he creates an interpretation that justifies a clinical intervention on the patient.

Reality can be such an extreme and distressing condition for some that the alternative they find is to build a wonderful world in which there are no rules other than those they create at their own pleasure and retreat there, refusing to leave for trivial reasons. With sailors, the situation may not have been different; given over to a wandering life and deprived of a destiny, all that melody led them to act out what they had created in their daydreams and lodge themselves in this fantasy, refusing to leave it, because doing so would deprive them of a state of pleasure, of ecstasy; in fact, this term is somewhat controversial, because no human being can leave themselves; there is only the possibility of entering so deeply into their own psychological world that they begin to ignore everything and everyone outside it and, in the case of the psychosis of shipwrecked people, they refuse reality to such an extent that they even deny their condition of death, or even not care about it. This is a very delicate aspect of existence, because each person can subject themselves to a psychotic state, depending on their

desire, driven [*or not*] by traumatic experiences and the ways in which these affect them and their state of psychic economy.

The central aspect of psychosis is the loss of contact with reality, depending on its intensity. At any given moment, the loss will be of greater or lesser intensity. When psychotics are not in crisis, they look after their well-being, eat, avoid hurting themselves, have sexual interest, and establish contact with real people. All of this is evidence of the existence of a relationship with the real world. Psychosis, properly speaking, begins from the point at which the patient relates to objects and things that do not exist in the sensible world; this is because, “in psychoses, some aspects of reality are denied and replaced by particular and peculiar conceptions that only meet the characteristics of the disease” (Boechat, 2017, p. 02).

To place here, as the aforementioned author does, the disease as an active subject and determinant of the condition of life and individual existence is to attempt to hijack the self-control and decision-making power that belongs to any human being. It would be more prudent to say that all of this meets the characteristics of the patient's desire. However, to admit such a situation is to end up not knowing how to resolve the impasse of individual freedom in which he may have desired that condition for himself, which would prevent any possibility of treatment, since the patient would refuse to declare the cause of his disease, since it provided him with pleasure and well-being.

The great enigma of the psychotic for Psychiatry and, especially, for Psychoanalysis is that he does not speak. Unlike the neurotic, he lives in a reality created by him and only for him. He lives, in this way, with total psychic autonomy; but, paradoxically, an existence totally uprooted from common reality and, as a result, becomes incapable of communicating, sharing and exchanging experiences with others. This can be an existential state that causes serious limitations to the individual, making him unhappy and excluded from situations of great relevance for the construction and structuring of human personology; but, here we can question to what extent this, in fact, is a reality experienced by the patient and accepted as such by himself?

Since psychosis is being treated from a psychoanalytic perspective and compared to neurosis, the latter causes the patient to seek help, even if in a strange way that is little understood by society in general. The neurotic's behavior reveals something that goes beyond the individual's own standards, to the point of bothering himself, at which point he feels the need for help to try to overcome and/or defeat his inner demons, a situation that does not happen with the psychotic, who, trapped in his world and talking to the ghosts he creates in his image and likeness, ends up finding the long-awaited peace of mind that everyone seeks, in some way.

Science seeks, in some way, to resolve the issue of psychosis, precisely because its condition on the individual offends society, since the patient ignores it and all community life. He begins to live alone, immersed in his wonderful world, in which he is not condemned to be free; he is, because he can talk and live in the way he pleases. Aristotle (384-322 BC) would say that this individual is a god or an animal, because only these two beings have the power and freedom to live alone, ignoring everything else. “The self needs to accommodate itself to this hallucinatory phenomenon, but it can only do so by paying the price of breaking with reality” (Santos and Oliveira, 2012, 76).

But now we return to the previous problem: does the break with objective reality represent a trauma or a deliberate decision by the individual in favor of his well-being and the maintenance of his psychic economy? Freud's analysis and interpretation lead him to this understanding of psychosis and the psychotic, a conclusion that led him to distance himself from his study and the target object of its accommodation, preferring neurosis and the neurotic as elements to be investigated through the technique he was developing. The point is that he was creating a technique based on a specific methodology and for it to work satisfactorily, he needed the patient to become involved in reality and express everything that bothered him, through catharsis. While working on his technique, he looked for a mental illness that fit the profile and, even though in his years of practice as a doctor he had delved into the study of psychoses and was interested in their etiology and behavior, he ended up discovering that everything came down to the patient and his search would end up being long enough to condemn him to failure regarding his goals, which was to create a new science.

Psychosis does not present a level of conflict that demonstrates a struggle between the Ego and the Superego. The former understands that it cannot live according to the demands of the latter and thus withdraws, consciously and deliberately, to a world where everything is perfect and balanced, that is, an idyllic place where there is no conflict of any kind and, strangely, the unconscious accepts this existential condition adopted by the individual, even feeding it with speeches produced by the individual himself, disguising them with voices known to the same person at some point and which have been recorded in his memory.

In the case of the castaways, enslaved by the song of the sirens, something deeper than this may have happened, since, facing certain death, they indulged in a state of introspection, talking to some figure from the past to whom they had promised to return one day and build a home and be a normal man living a normal life, even if this was nothing more than a delirium brought on by too much wine. Once captured in this idyllic dream, there was no escape from it except through death. In some way, still unexplained, the Greeks knew that this condition of

outrageous alienation was caused by that melodious music, which bewitched them to the point of dominating them, subjugating their wills and destroying their ability to think rationally.

THE PSYCHOSIS OF SHIPWRECKERS

The object of analysis and exploration in this article is the *psychosis of shipwrecked sailors*, in which the first person to bring it into a possibility of interpretation and study was Homer (9th century BC), who, through his art, transformed a rock into creatures of extraordinary beauty and irresistible sensuality (the sirens). When these beings sang, they attracted sailors who were unable to fight against their power of seduction. Obsessed by that supernatural melody, the pilots hurled their ships against the rocks of the island, they sank, and the sirens devoured the crew.

In Homer's *Odyssey*, the sorceress Circe describes the Sirens sitting surrounded by piles of rotting human bones. "The Sirens, whose voice enchants all men who approach them. If someone, unaware, approaches them and hears them, his wife and his little children will never again gather around him, for he will be captivated by the harmonious song of the Sirens. They live in a meadow, around which are piled the bones of rotting bodies, whose skins are drying out" (Homer, 2000, p. 158).

The poet's description is precise and meticulous about the sailors who were wasting away on top of the cliff, dying from starvation and acute dehydration. What they were able to explain was through mythology and it all came down to the enchantment caused by the music that the mermaids expressed endlessly, fulfilling a sacred mission. However, there were conditions of malnutrition that caused such delirious situations, as we now know, caused especially by the lack of B vitamins.

None of these conditions were appropriate for the historical moment in which Homer tells the stories of the murderous sea nymphs and, to clarify that the ancients did not describe them, leaving this to the scholiasts, the legends about them were very ancient, referring to the time when the Goddess Demeter was sovereign, alongside Zeus and he was not yet called the father of the gods. There is another version of the legend, little known and little known, that the Sirens were half birds and half women, thus transformed so that they could fly over the world in an attempt to find Demeter's missing daughter, Persephone. It is a complex story and not strong enough to convince, because it goes against the tradition of marriage by kidnapping to which the Young Lady had been subjected by her uncle Lord Hades.

The shape of the mermaids that has survived to this day was created by scholiast poets, who explained that in ancient mythology there was no mention of them being half fish and half women. All of this is more like stories from sailors with severe mental disorders and that, later on, the most fantastic lucubrations were created, obeying the characteristics of poetic license and the acceptance of the public who recorded them in books, with this version being the most accepted due to the fact that it was possible to record it on paper.

What is striking is the huge number of men who deliberately launched their boats against the rocks where the monsters were and died there from hunger and thirst, exposed to the sun. Knowing that the number was high, it is worth noting that this was recorded in history, with warnings to avoid crossing that maritime region, at the risk of being swallowed up by a horrible and painful death. According to the poets, the individuals died without knowing they were dying, as if consumed by an extremely alienating psychological situation.

In the classical tradition, the Sirens are described as threatening and voracious. Their threatening and voracious side is perhaps one of the most striking and present in Greek mythology. “ The Sirens were nymphs, famous for the sweetness of their song. They were transformed by Demeter into sea monsters for not opposing the abduction of her companion, Persephone. They had the head and body of a woman and, with their harmonious voice, attracted sailors who passed by the Sirensian Reefs or Syrenian Islands. There were three Sirens: Parthenope, Lucosia and Ligeia. The oracle had predicted to them that they would live as long as they could detain those who passed by the sea; as soon as someone managed to pass by them, without succumbing to the charm of their voices, they would perish. Thus these enchanting nymphs made such good use of their fascination that their victims no longer thought of returning to their own country, and, forgetting to eat and drink, died of starvation. When Ulysses passed by them, using a stratagem, he was able to delight himself in the music of the sirens and escape unharmed. The sirens, realizing that their efforts were useless, threw themselves into the sea, where two of them were transformed into rocks. One of them, Parthenope, was swept by the waves to the coast of Italy, where they erected a tomb for her and built a city that was named in her honor. Later, the name of the city was changed to New Town, i.e., Naples” (Spalding, 1974, p. 244).

Many of the mythological characters helped to create great future stories, involving cities, men, women, rulers, and Italy would be no different, especially because it belonged to Greek territory, that is, it is Greek, *par excellence* ; therefore, a Greek mermaid from the archaic era ending up on the Italian coast is nothing more than a whim, a convenience. One condition that is revealed is the assumption that they knew her very well, even knowing her name, and,

in order to build a city with her name, it shows that she was worshipped in that region, receiving prayers and libations; which allows us to deduce that the news of her death was mourned and caused great commotion.

We know of a stratagem used by Ulysses, which was to tie one of his men who had gone mad to the mast of his ship, so that he would not throw himself into the sea towards the enchanting beasts and thus perish. He had received a spell from Circe that protected him from the madness caused by the wonderful song, and he was able to pass by the Sirenus Islands and still enjoy the beautiful music. Jason and the Argonauts took the lyrist Orpheus on the ship Argos who, with the music of his lyre, overcame the wonderful sound of the murderous muses of Sirenus. Not all sailors were overcome by the fever that made them mad to the point of being conquered by the sound of the Sirens. There must have been some other element that provoked all this loss of contact with reality to such an extent that those attacked died in a slow and painful way, as if they had been condemned to a penalty from which they could not escape, resigning themselves to a fatal destiny.

However, this state of psychic resignation to a tragic end is not human; humans fight to the end to overcome their state of weakness and, furthermore, such a state of alienation cannot be characterized as a common illness, explainable by any science whatsoever; hence the Greeks said that such men were under a spell, alienated and anesthetized in such a way that they completely lost contact with reality. It was their behavioral attitude of intense passivity in the face of imminent death that made ancient thinkers dedicate themselves for hours to intense analysis, in an attempt to understand the situation and, if the scholiasts persisted in this search for clarification, this intrinsically reveals that such was not achieved.

Even though the myth of the sirens was created after great masters dedicated themselves to the study of the phenomenon, such as giving half-human, half-fish forms to the bloodthirsty and deadly creatures, following a principle of making Greek literature a vast landmark of fantastic stories, what is implied is that before this enchanting adornment that has reached the present day through Homer's narrative, what, in fact, intrigued the intellectuals of Antiquity? This question leads us to think that the rulers of the cities that needed to navigate through that region recruited men of great wisdom and knowledge in an attempt to solve the great evil; financing intensely in-depth investigations.

These monsters were not well regarded by sailors or merchants; but, as it was a curse from a very powerful mother goddess, there was no way to simply make them disappear, so it was up to them to discover how to prevent sailors from going mad and crashing their ships into the rocks. What conclusions did the investigators reach about how to avoid the tragedy? Homer

mentions that Ulysses ordered his sailors to put wax in their ears so they would not succumb to the Sirens' song. This strategy created by the aedo can be taken as poetic license or as a representation of the stories he had heard about how sailors learned to outwit the man-eating nymphs.

Castaway psychosis is a psychological condition that is caused by a series of physical factors, such as hunger, intense thirst and fatigue, sunstroke, excess salt intake, which increases body pain and the desolation that comes from all this. Many films describe sailors and/or ordinary people on the high seas seeing islands with solid ground where there is nothing. This form of psychotic illusion may also be a way for the *id to protect itself* against despair, which could lead such people to commit suicide. Thus, given that the unconscious works to maintain life, it would cause such hallucinations as a way of trying to protect the individual. And, if this assertion were taken as a basis for understanding psychosis, it would be possible to affirm, or at least assume, that when human thought enters the psychotic process, the individual would be seeking some type of protection against external reality, more specifically trying to guide it to remain safe, even if it is under a condition that deviates from a valid and socially accepted profile.

How did this mental disorder occur in men condemned to death by starvation, who, by their apparent behavior, completely lost the notion that they were dying in a painful and cruel way, imposed on themselves by themselves, and, quite possibly, this was what challenged the wisdom and wise men of the time. The attitude of men, until a few moments before coming into contact with the sound of the muses, was that of someone normal, and suddenly, everything became a fight against death because of the shipwreck and then the unquestionable surrender of this to a horrendous and pitiful end. All kinds of offerings must have been made to these sea nymphs and, judging by how they were interpreted by the scholiasts, nothing had any kind of effect on them. Nor could it have, because the curse they received from the goddess Demeter linked them to Greek pragmatism, whose destiny was to kill all who tried to cross that region. And destiny was inexorable.

Here, the issue of the legend of the mermaids is brought up because this was the greatest manifestation of psychotic delirium on the high seas that has come down to our days through classical literature. Quite possibly, because of the stories and myths that were told among ancient peoples, there is no doubt that images of women with fish tails could not have been reported by sailors as being real. According to Spalding (1974), "it is likely that the legend of the mermaids has its origin in the sometimes melodious noise that the waves make when they break against the reefs" (p. 244). And this sound was so intoxicating, attractive, and melodious

that it led the most ignorant of men to seek a meaning for their lives; failing to find it, they would prostrate themselves and give themselves over to a slow death, because they had no reason to continue.

The tales tell that no man could resist that enchanting music and, if so, how did they become aware of the situation and even to the point where there were eyewitnesses who could narrate the terrifying scenes they witnessed, even from afar? The sound produced by the waves crashing against the rocks must have been so rhythmic that it resembled a woman singing a song in a single note, so serene and in tune, without any interruption, leading the listener to be hypnotized by that sound sequence.

Losing contact with reason and alienating oneself from the external world is a task that demands effort from the unconscious and conflict with the conscious that does not give in. Somewhere in the mind, the individual fights against all this. As narrated by the poets, the state of psychosis that took hold of the sailors could not be only the result of the music of the sirens, because the conditions described were degrading, provoking adverse feelings of all kinds in any mortal. However, a psychotic person can see, hear, feel and perceive things that only they can, or the opposite can also be true, the condition of losing all senses and living immersed solely in the illusion produced by their sick brain.

No study, not even one from Antiquity that may have survived, can explain who were the individuals who ended up bewitched by the music exuded by the soprano voice of the demonic sea nymphs. Based on Homer's work and knowing that both he and his men had been away from home for more than two decades, we can come close to defining the profile of the psychotics attracted by the melodious song; they were individuals who had already lost all hope of reuniting with their old lives and having access to their homes and their respective spouses and children. Possibly, these men had long since alienated themselves from conscious life and, upon hearing the seductive music, the act of launching their ships against the rocks and taking refuge with the objects of their illusion was the swan song of their miserable lives, already devoid of any existential meaning.

Azen (2012) clarifies that,

Most studies on the origin of the mermaid myth believe that the legend of the mermaids arose because of the sound that the winds made when they hit the steep rocks of some Mediterranean islands. The howling winds hit the rocks and reverberated because of the waters. This generated a soft, high-pitched sound that was mistaken for women singing. Sailors at that time, when there was no technology, spent months at sea steering their ships based on brute force, far from their wives and far from any female company, and this made

them extremely needy of female affection and care, in addition to obviously having an immense sexual need (Azen, 2012, p. 02).

Scholars are very concerned with understanding the origin of myth; but they ignore the fact that tales did not emerge randomly, as a product of the imagination of aeds and rhapsodes and, later, of scholiasts. There was an entire sociological process that preceded this, discussions about situations that could not be explained by *Logos*, and this approach leads to another interpretation about the emergence of rational thought, the use of empirical investigation in order to clarify some problems that transformed the lives of residents and merchants in regions of archaic Greece. Here we have to say that contemplation, speculation and empirical observation were not distant from each other, separated as is currently considered erudite science, although there was a space of time to analyze the data collected through thought, raising hypotheses and creating explanations that proved to be plausible.

Thus, the myth was created not as a way of explaining the phenomenon itself, but as a way of enriching the set of fantastic stories, transforming Greek literature into the richest in the entire West. They did not recognize psychology as an explanatory element of life and existence; however, anthropology and sociology were two sciences that formed the entire epistemological basis of the ancient Greek world (archaic and classical). In the absence of an enlightening explanation about the cause of the madness that struck sailors in that region, they declared that there was a magical force that dominated them and caused them, as if bewitched and without any control over their intrinsic wills, to commit the insane act of throwing their ships against the rocks, perishing in the most horrifying way ever seen.

To link the madness of the dying to unsatisfied sexual desire is to stretch the understanding of psychosis too far, especially since what has survived to this day about the sailors' posture demonstrates that they were contemplating something while they still had vital strength, and very possibly, the position of their dominant hand indicated a fruitless attempt to reach something [*or someone*]. Taking this condition as a *leitmotif* for a broader deduction, this imaginary someone, the product of their hallucination, could well be a woman; but, under no circumstances, would she be seeking genetic satisfaction; it would be salvation, but not from death; it would be a violent desire to appease longing.

Without analyzing the entire geographical, economic and social context of Greece, focusing only on the creation of the tale itself, it is almost impossible to reach a plausible understanding of the origin of the myth of the sirens. What is analyzed is that they are the product of a curse; but that they consulted an oracle in order to know when their torture would end and, here is the paradox, as long as they seduced and lured sailors to their deaths, enchanting

them with their beautiful voices of prepubescent children, they would continue to live. For that fateful condition to end, it would be enough for them to let someone escape alive; but that was not the case and they performed their function [*not of singing to exalt the beauties of the spirit; rather, to kill*] with painstaking perfection, because a capricious and spiteful god demanded it be so and destiny determined that it would be so, and so it was done.

All that was missing for all this to be completed in a perfect determination was for the same music that inspired one towards life to do so towards death; but how could this be achieved? It needed to create a special type of psychic pathology in which the patient could not fight against the terrible external conditions to which he was subjected. It was not just being drawn towards a cruel and exhausting death; the bewitched person needed to lose his connection with the world and with everything that made sense to him; but here he is faced, once again, with another paradox, because it was through his connection with what was most profound and sublime in his life that he accepted alienation from the external world.

What Homer described in the form of a fiction can be interpreted as *Castaway Psychosis*. Intensive days lost at sea provoke “a kind of collective hallucination, in which sailors come to live in a shared imaginary world. The illusions may include comforting images of home [...] they may find themselves involved in conversations with deceased shipmates and dead family members, while losing all sense of time” (Philbrick, 2001, p. 134).

This explanation already allows us to get closer to what the psychosis of shipwrecked people really is and how it manifests itself, in which there is a noticeable loss of reason until it finally culminates in a complete alienation from reality, this event happening to individuals who, until recently, were conscious and in full control of their mental faculties. Since the wise men of Antiquity did not find an answer that could clarify, at the very least, such situations of passage from one condition to another in an extremely short space of time, the only explanation that seemed plausible to them was that some magical effect was falling upon these men, a curse from which it was impossible to escape.

This does not mean, under any circumstances, that the Greeks of the Ancient Age [*archaic*] were dominated by mysticism and superstition. Quite the contrary, before appealing to the supernatural they sought empirical answers that would allow them to understand the phenomenon. Even if they found them, it was not natural that they dared to offer them to everyone, because it could be useful to them as an instrument of social control and so it was, because by relegating to the gods all types of catastrophic situations that befell mortals, the priests gained a type of power that they had never even dreamed of.

It is only natural that the Greeks already knew about paranoid delusions and loss of sense of reality during long periods exposed to the terrible conditions of navigation and the exhaustion caused by the sea. Likewise, they must have already known some treatment or that the crisis would be temporary, considering that one of the sailors in Ulysses' entourage was tied to the mast of the ship, in order to prevent him from committing suicide during his delirium; he was released soon after they crossed the place of terror caused by the song of the hungry muses of the sea who devour men.

Everything leads to the understanding that the wise men of Antiquity were familiar with the problem of the seduction of the sirens and could do nothing but seek strategies that would help overcome the evil; but, judging by the story that began to surround the origin of the sirens, characterized by the powerful pragmatic bias, everything indicates that nothing that was tried, as a way of resisting their musical charms, proved to be up to the task, continuing with their terrible fate until someone appeared who managed to resist the melody. It may be just a legend, someone who was never found after having accomplished the feat; but it served for Homer to personify the end of the curse to his hero's efforts and that, let it be clarified, it was not he who killed them; they committed suicide, which shows that they were considered characters of great value and high respect by society.

The question that arises is whether there was no way to overcome the sirens, because of the condition to which they were condemned, that they would die the day a human resisted their song, that is, because of this divine sentence they constantly dedicated themselves to perfecting it so that no one would escape, not being satisfied with perfectionism, they sought excellence, *areté*. They clung so tightly to their destinies, imposed on them because of their negligence towards Demeter's daughter, Korè (the Maiden) and, perhaps this was the curse to which they were condemned, to cling to life as their ultimate goal, knowing that this attachment represented condemnation for countless others, without the slightest condition of overcoming such a fateful condition. On the other hand, there is the issue that there was no known cure for psychosis and, in the absence of a minimally efficient or effective treatment, the best solution would be to keep the primary cause of the misfortunes alive, because without this, what would be left to take its place in explaining the phenomenon?

Homer, the first of many who would provoke the beginning of the imminent process of [*attempted*] destruction of the mythology of Greek mythology, takes care to make the Oracle's prophecy about the sirens come true; even because his hero needed to return home; but, in the same way, he could take another route; but, no, he had to provoke the change from mythical

thinking to logical thinking, opening a field so that atheist philosophers could shout their concepts, visions, intuitions and interpretations according to their ideologies.

In the case of Homer's work, the hallucination that afflicted Ulysses was related to Penelope, his wife, and Telemachus, his son, and his home, the Island of Ithaca, since this was his most intense desire. The sailors, who had been away from women for so long, it was natural for their reptilian brains to see beauties available. Here we are faced with a paradox, in the scene where Odysseus has the southern winds stored in a bag so that they would not hinder his return home; he is betrayed by his men, who believe he is betraying them regarding their return home, which was also theirs. This perception already places the sailors as individuals who also dreamed of their homes and their respective families; not just sex and wine.

Everything indicates that the prejudice against one class, that of sailors, contributed to the study of the song of the sirens and their hypnotic effect on them, which already determined the reason why they became alienated from reality and went towards them, no longer measuring the notion of danger and giving themselves over to death in a fateful manner. It turns out that the psychotic state that took hold of the sailors was very strange, because as if dominated by an imperious force they aimed their ships against the rocks, putting everything at risk, including the entire cargo and the crew. It was not an isolated act in which, possessed by the melodious music, they threw themselves into the sea, swimming towards the illusion produced by the sick mind and allowing themselves to waste away from the heat, thirst and hunger.

All of this analysis, carried out so far, about the psychosis of the castaways demonstrates that their symptoms went far beyond the classic symptomatic disorder that explains the loss of connection with objective reality. It was not just an act of insanity and a desire to die or to set out in search of an alienating relief with the image of a long-lost possession projected towards any object, in the middle of nowhere, in which such hallucination was being driven by unparalleled music. Even at the time, the wise men who were assigned to investigate and provide an enlightening answer about the phenomenon were unable to do so, despite already having contact with psychosis and other types of psychic disorders. What type of conflict between the ego and the external world were the victims of the demonic adolescent nymphs carrying? At the very moment they directed their boats towards the rocks, they had no idea of the horrifying condition of death that would befall them next; They were already lost in their inner worlds, disconnected from any kind of reality and even their respective subjectivities were no longer able to free them from any suffering that was being inflicted on them by the unhealthy conditions of the open sea.

The castaways' psychosis did not represent any symptom of alienation or hallucination; there was something much deeper involved in the process of self-exclusion from existence and life, and the unraveling of reality cannot be so intense that someone dies in ecstasy with their own hallucinogenic creation. At some point, this construction ceases to arouse any kind of pleasure and the unconscious itself induces the individual to come out of their psychotic trance, as a form of survival.

This very thought may well have occurred to the wise men of Antiquity, when they analyzed the situation in which the seductions of the devourers of the sea took place and how the unfortunates who became their prey ended up. What was going on in the minds of those men, condemned to an unprecedented death and, even if they could be saved, at some point, what lucidity would remain in their minds? One must think that, for some reason, some castaway caught in the sonorous web of the soprano nymphs was saved; but, the remnants of violence made it impossible for them to live again.

The survivors of the whaler *Essex*, which sank in 1820 after being attacked by a male sperm whale, suffered from lack of food and water, excessive heat and exposure to the sun, and one of them, when he returned to his normal life in his village, suffered from headaches that did not stop. The deprivations to which the castaways are subjected cannot be repaired, and even affect their judgment and their existential conditions. Thus, we once again ask ourselves what the psychosis of the castaways really means, because to say that it is a condition of severe alienation is to be too modest in relation to its devastating power. What elements lead to its formation in the minds of such individuals? Considering that this loss of contact with reality and the appearance of situations that only the patient feels, sees and perceives is what is exposed and from this a hypothesis is constructed and, more carefully, a theory; but what exists in their psychic world that is not revealed? What underpins this individual space?

Aristotle (384-322 BC) was the first to state that all knowledge passes through the senses. However, madness and insanity, as well as psychosis, are also productions that have a sensitive origin. This is characterized as an abnormal state of psychic functioning. The ideal world created by the psychotic is an antithesis of the world in which he is represented or a return to this paradisiacal place, which proves that he has a perception of reality. Thus, it follows that,

The mechanisms of psychosis point to a disturbance in the relationship between the ego and the external world. In acute hallucinatory confusion, the external world is not perceived at all or its perception has no effect. In *amentia* not only is the acceptance of new perceptions refused; also the internal world, which, as a copy of the external world, has hitherto represented it, loses its significance (its *cathexis*). The ego autocratically creates a new external and

internal world, and there can be no doubt about two facts: that this new world is constructed in accordance with the wishful impulses of the id and that the reason for this dissociation from the external world is some very serious frustration of a wish on the part of reality - a frustration that seems intolerable (Freud, [1923] 2006, pp. 89-90).

Sigmund is very objective in his explanation of psychosis, and it is strange that he did not at least try to delve more deeply into the subject, because his approach is precise and enlightening, presenting the behavior that the psychotic person develops as a way of avoiding the pain and disappointment suffered in the external world. What frustration this was is a complex investigation, because it is not a momentary situation or a condition in which he felt powerless, but that he could overcome with time. It is something that is completely beyond his reach and power.

Taking Freud's thought as a leitmotif to approach a more categorical understanding of psychosis, the feeling of frustration is so deep and melancholic that even the possibility of verbalizing the problem is interrupted by the individual's own brain. It is as if the unconscious dominated him and tried, in a very strange way, to protect him from a pain that would not kill him, but that would consume him until there was nothing left from which to extract more suffering.

If this is the case, could one even consider the idea that psychosis is a form of protection given to the individual against possible emotional decline? If so, what kind of world does he create in his unconscious? Interpreting psychosis from Sigmund's perspective, this would be a place where the frustration he had suffered does not exist, because the tangible and intangible elements that lead to it have been excluded from this space created to be perfect.

Still using Freud's thinking as a basis for understanding the psychosis of shipwrecked sailors, such frustration, to the point that the sailors surrendered to a dramatic and melancholic end, could only be with their own life, as a whole, in which there was nothing to justify their existence and, in the same way, there was frustration with the afterlife, because he did not commit suicide; he died, without knowing why or even that he was dying, because he was lost in a world that was alien and strange to everything that existed around him. Perhaps, in his delirious moments, he was thinking about the existence in which he could, at least, be happy, have a family, live by their side, be with them at all times and, there was no way to ask them for forgiveness, because he was in a condition of reality. For him, what he was experiencing, as an intrinsic *delirium demens*, was his essence as a human being.

If this is the case, psychosis is a narcissistic act taken to the most extreme of reality; because this paradisiacal world cannot be shared with anyone, being exclusive to the patient,

who withdraws into it, because of a frustration that he did not know how to deal with or that he was not able to do so, leaving all those who love him out, condemning them to a suffering that they do not understand, a mixture of anger and pity, while he exempts himself from all types of suffering; so much so that he refuses to free himself from the evil in which he finds himself.

The patient's condition presents itself in various ways, the most common being through delusions and other types of strange behavior, such as muteness; sometimes saying things that seem to have no connection with reality; however, the patient's brain remains active, creating and recreating situations that function according to his own desires. What drives this particular process in order to create a particular condition continues to be the great challenge of research, precisely because what represents an innocent frustration for one person may be something exorbitant for another; each person, in particular, can determine the degree of violence with which things affect him.

Delirium is the main symptom of psychosis, which can arise from a memory to which the individual begins to give a new interpretation. This was what happened to sailors since pre-Homeric times. However, this maritime psychosis was caused by the music of the waters in contact with the rocks. And music is a type of art that invades the human mind, reaching its innermost depths without asking permission, penetrating the most inaccessible recesses of the individual and awakening long-forgotten ghosts. It is no wonder that the legend enchanted the poet and his readers, becoming an object of study *ipso facto*. "The soft sound that was generated by the rocks worked as a trigger in the minds of those men, which even generated mirages of women, something similar to what happens to those who walk through the desert and want so much to find water that they see water where there is only sand" (Azen, 2012, p. 02).

The most interesting thing about the analysis of the myth of the mermaids and their enchantment through the wonderful music they emanated is that theorists are absolutely certain that the sailors visualized only women in their deliriums, that is, making a direct reference to sex for sex's sake. It cannot be so decisive that a single element conditions the individual himself to a state of alienation such that he is completely disconnected from all conscious life, allowing himself to die in the most exhausting misery and suffering.

At no time did the scholiasts and other scholars of Antiquity describe the delusions of the dying shipwrecked victims of the sirens. According to them, they were nymphs of exuberant beauty, which leaves room for interpretation, because their power of enchantment came from their childlike soprano voices. They were not the ones who placed the hallucinations in the thoughts of their prey; their power was not so potent and it so happened that, even having captured the unfortunate, they needed to continue singing in order to maintain the spell. The

description given for the delusional content was the work of modern interpreters, especially after the creation of Psychoanalysis, in which it is assumed that Sigmund sexualized all human existence along with its actions. The world created to be inhabited by the psychotic; in fact, a space produced by himself, based on his own convictions, is not open to visitors and, for this simple reason, [*almost*] impossible to interpret and, if so, it becomes [*almost*] impossible to understand it, making deductions and theoretical approximations feasible and, in cases of in-depth studies, where one has the opportunity to accompany individuals who believe themselves to be painters, one knows that he is painting; making it impossible to know what he is painting, whether animal, human, or plant...

An illustration of this situation is represented by Miguel de Cervantes (1547-1616), in his work *Don Quixote* (1605-1615) when the Knight of the Sad Countenance, Alonso Quijano, comes across a painter who is painting a picture. Don Quixote asks him about what he is painting and the painter replies: *Whatever will be!* Not even the artist knew what was going on in his mind; he let himself be given over to whatever his unconscious determined, alienated from reality in such a way that his answer clarifies the way he perceives it and demonstrates his degree of interest in it and in everything that involves it, represents it, directly and indirectly.

Freud interprets psychosis based on the man of the late 19th and early 20th centuries, driven by a process of industrialization and urbanization of existence in a singular way, in which there was no longer any way to escape the attributes of madness, social sanctions and the mechanization of his life; so that this individual needed to escape from himself, not necessarily from the society in which he lived. The sailors of Antiquity may well have fit into this same existential profile, seeking an escape from their own worlds in their own world, because there was no other place to go where they would be masters of their own lives, since life in Hades was marked by rigid rules and the strangest judgments, if not equal to those they faced on Earth, perhaps even more severe and heinous. In this sense, the only alternative that presented itself to them was to escape to a space where they were absolute masters and the rules were dictated by themselves, that is, there would be no rules; only the absolute satisfaction of the supreme desire, whatever it might be. This is a very complex point to understand, because the boundary between madness and sanity is so tenuous and undefined, technically, because even if a term could be presented to determine it, societies, with their cultures and values, give it meanings that cannot be interpreted in a Cartesian way.

Through the psychotic process, the individual, consciously aware that he is breaking a powerful social rule, exempts himself from total responsibility. “ In this way, men’s inconsistencies, eccentricities and follies would appear in a light similar to their sexual

perversions, through the acceptance of which they spare themselves repression” (FREUD, [1923] 2006, p. 91).

This statement by Freud leads to the conclusion that the psychotic individual is aware of what he does and does not submit to social rules for convenience, since the alienated condition absolves him of blame for his direct actions. The greatest affront this individual commits to society is his denial of it through his silence, which may even be muteness, an act of revolt against everyone and not specifically against a special degrading condition that is attacking him.

It is not surprising that the psychosis of shipwrecked sailors caused such a stir among the ancient scholars that they studied the phenomenon and that it has come down to the present day as a *mythos* and not as a legend of the sea. Even though the root cause of the sailors' hallucinations and state of alienation has not been discovered, many speculations have been made and presented, the most widely accepted being that the waves of the sea crashing against the rocks produced such perfect and wonderful music that it provoked daydreams and led individuals to a state of detachment from all objective reality. In the midst of this interpretation, another question arises: why, exactly, in this specific place and not in other parts of the Mediterranean? It is assumed that the phenomenon had only been observed in this location; but this is an interesting question, because what natural elements converged to produce such a sound?

It may have been in the complete absence of conditions to explain the occurrence of such a geographical phenomenon that the scholiasts and poets of Classical Antiquity were able to link the presence of the murderous soprano muses to the curse cast upon them by the Goddess Demeter, as punishment for not having denounced the abduction of Persephone. The wrath of the goddess of agriculture lasted forever, until Homer decided to put an end to it, beginning a cycle of destruction of religious sentiment in Greece and of mythology itself.

CONCLUSION

Psychosis is related to a relative or total loss of contact with external reality and to claim that there is a noticeable loss of internal reality would not be a denial of reality at all, basing such thought on the behavior presented by the patient; however, it is a situational condition that is very difficult to confirm, since the psychotic person does not express himself through words and, in most cases, the analyst must seek to understand his silence, in order to then interpret it and its generic and specific causes. This makes it very difficult, if not almost impossible, to

treat this disease through psychoanalysis, being possible only by an in-depth study of the causes that possibly led the patient to the threshold of sanity, leading him to cross the line that separates it from madness.

What does this situation, in particular, offer to individuals that makes them remain trapped in their intrinsic worlds, without expressing the desire to return to objective reality? For them, it is a special desire to remain there without feeling bothered by anything, even because they completely lose contact with external reality. What causes this condition in the human being that goes beyond the situation of trauma, in which an ego-dystonic, a Dionysian behavior is formed, in the words of Nietzsche, in order to have, in the patient's thinking, an ego-syntonic state, an Apollonian balance. In psychosis, in its deepest state, there is no manifestation of any approximation of a desire to live with the world or with anyone who is not in the psychotic's thinking.

When it came to analyzing the psychosis of shipwrecked sailors, a question arose regarding the understanding of the above: if the myth was created by Homer, about women who were half human and half fish, he heard it from someone, since he was blind. However, if these stories came to everyone's knowledge through sailors, then we have here that the psychosis of these individuals was linked, in some way, to the maternal figure, in which the desire for pleasure was linked to a *taboo*, in which the son had access to the mother's body; but only from the waist up, for the pleasure of satisfying hunger, not directly and exclusively to the genetic pleasure.

Therefore, we have to say that the sailors' object projection was not linked to prostitutes; but to their own mothers, to their wives as caregivers, and not even their unconscious manifestations expressed sexual desire; rather, it was a welcome, a return to the womb, to the maternal lap, where the evil and violence of life had not yet reached them, and the security promoted by this figure allowed them to live as in an enchanted dream, in a world created by themselves, by unknown psychological mechanisms. In any case, the analysis presented by Freud is deliberately clear: the psychotic creates a fantastic world based on reminiscences of his childhood, leading a return to it or a denial of it, in which the sources of pleasure and/or displeasure are active and, once combined with the conditions of health and psychic economy, can cause a collapse of intellectual balance, leading to a state of alienation from objective reality.

There is a need for further studies, analyses and interpretations of the texts and in what contexts they were written and by whom, in fact, which would allow us to achieve a closer

understanding of what really caused the delirium in the sailors' thoughts, especially regarding those who were adrift on the high seas, with little chance of finding salvation.

But, given the way the phenomenon was treated by ancient thinkers, it was not a case of vagabonds and sailors without proper social support who were struck by the disease and gave themselves up to death on the rock of the murderous nymphs, lost in a parallel world, impossible to be analyzed and interpreted by reason. The only explanation that the wise men of the time found for that situation was that those men were bewitched by something and, after intense studies, possibly some of them, even of an empirical nature, taking Homer's narrative as the object and point of interpretation, they deduced that it was that enchanting and soft music like that of a passionate soprano that was the cause of all the evil. Thus, the solution was to avoid that space in the sea; if that was not possible, they would plug their ears with wax; if not, they would be captured and devoured alive by the muses of the sea.

There was no salvation for those who were captured by the Sirens and their spell, the intoxicating melody that took the individual to a world from which they could not escape or which, of their own free will, they did not want to leave. This is the great mystery that challenged the Greeks of Antiquity, the scholiasts of Classical Antiquity and persists to this day, through studies involving madness and its variants, including psychosis and its consequences.

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